

Beyond Conflict: The Erasure of Palestine and Palestinians in Zionist Thought and Violence

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Framing Israel's attack on Gaza as a conflict is in itself a key misconception. Israel's attack on Gaza is *not* a conflict, even though it followed the Hamas-led attack on Israel on October 7, 2023. This misconception structures efforts in the West, including in Western academia, to minimize, blur, disavow, and deny the character of Israel as a settler colonial state. The distorted lens of “conflict,” in other words, legitimizes the basic oppressive relationship between Zionist colonizers and colonized Palestinians. As Zionist leader Zéev Jabotinsky puts it in “The Iron Wall,” his seminal text from 1923, “Colonisation can have only one aim, and Palestine Arabs cannot accept this aim,” so that “Zionist colonisation must either stop, or else proceed regardless of the native population” (Jabotinsky 1923).

And proceed it did, so that the creation of Israel in the 1948 War was the Palestinian Nakba—the mass deportations of 750,000 Palestinians amidst massacres of 15,000 Palestinians, and the destruction of hundreds of Palestinian towns and villages. Denial of the Nakba has therefore figured as a hallmark of the denial of Israel as a settler colonial state (Nassar 2023). It is remarkable, then, that Israeli leaders, politicians, and journalists have used the word Nakba numerous times since the October 7 attacks, now admitting the

1948 Nakba and pushing for a “second Nakba.” For example, Ariel Kallner, a member of the Knesset (Israeli parliament) representing the ruling Likud party, called on October 7, 2023, on X, formerly Twitter, for “Nakba to the enemy now. ... Nakba! Nakba that will overshadow the Nakba of 1948” (Kallner 2023). Indeed, the scale of killing and destruction in Gaza has now exceeded that of the destruction of Palestinian life and culture during the 1948 Nakba. Israel has killed more than 30,000 Palestinians, wounded over 70,000, and forcibly displaced nearly the entire population of 2.3 million people (UN OCHA 2024). Israeli war cabinet minister Avi Dichter described this “second Nakba” on Israeli TV on November 11, 2023, as “the Gaza Nakba” (Middle East Eye 2023). Perpetrators usually do not move from denial to recognition, so we should take note when they do.

A plan for the forced removal of all Palestinians in Gaza to the Sinai desert, across the Egyptian border, was in fact outlined in a document from the Israeli Ministry of Intelligence a month earlier, on October 13, 2023 (Abraham 2023). This is not a language of conflict, but of mass violence, which the International Court of Justice (ICJ) depicted as plausibly genocide in its provisional ruling on January 26, 2024, in the case of South Africa against Israel (ICJ 2024). In a speech to Israe-

lis on January 13, 2024, Israeli Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu responded to the South African case against Israel at the ICJ by casting Hamas as Nazis. More specifically, Netanyahu said that Israeli soldiers had found in Gaza a tablet of a girl with a photo of Hitler as its screensaver (i24News English 2024). No evidence for this has surfaced, not even in Israeli media, but Netanyahu knew that Israelis did not require evidence to support the idea that Palestinians in Gaza are Nazis, as it has been articulated in various ways in Israeli politics and media since the October 7 attacks. The focus in this case on a Palestinian child, in the context of an attack that has already killed over 12,000 Palestinian children, renders this image thoroughly genocidal.

This weaponization of the Holocaust erases Israeli history and turns the world upside down. It puts forward a narrative where a powerless people, forcibly displaced and attacked through decades of Israeli settler colonialism, military occupation, and siege are depicted as the worst perpetrators in modern imagination. This image then casts the settler colonial state, armed with nuclear weapons, and backed by its western allies, as the ultimate victim.

A war against Nazis is not a conflict; rather, it requires, in Israeli minds, the lifting “of all restrictions,” as Israeli Defense Minister Yoav Gallant explained on October 10, 2023 (Jones 2024). It is therefore urgent for scholars committed to documented truths, including political scientists, to recognize the horrible truth articulated both long ago by Jabotinsky and very recently by Dichter—that Zionism is premised on the destruction of Palestinians. It is urgent because we will fail to address this reality without recognizing it. And it is urgent because it remains a condition for envisioning other futures, beyond the Iron Wall. ♦

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